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A General Review of Phoenixin and Its Physiological Effects

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ABSTRACT

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Phoenixin (PNX) is a neuropeptide identified in 2013 and derived from the precursor protein known as small integral membrane protein 20, which is highly conserved throughout evolution. Two active isoforms, namely phoenixin-14 and phoenixin-20, have been identified, and these peptides are known to exhibit a wide distribution in both central and peripheral tissues. PNX is highly expressed particularly in the hypothalamus, as well as in brain regions associated with reproduction, appetite regulation, autonomic control, and emotional responses. Additionally, its presence has been demonstrated in the pituitary gland and several peripheral organs, suggesting its broad physiological relevance. The effects of PNX are largely mediated through the G protein-coupled receptor 173 (GPR173). This interaction contributes to the regulation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal axis through a close functional relationship with the gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) system. PNX has been shown to stimulate luteinizing hormone release, influence the reproductive cycle, and modulate gonadal hormone levels. Furthermore, depending on the site and route of administration, PNX may exert variable effects on appetite and fluid intake. Regarding cognitive functions, PNX has been reported to possess memory-enhancing and anxiolytic properties and to be involved in stress responses. From a metabolic perspective, PNX is suggested to play roles in adipogenesis, glucose homeostasis, and pancreatic hormone secretion. Moreover, protective effects within the cardiovascular system and suppression of inflammatory responses are considered among the important physiological functions of PNX. In conclusion, PNX is a pleiotropic neuropeptide involved in numerous physiological systems, including reproduction, energy metabolism, neurological processes, and inflammation. Nevertheless, further studies are required to better elucidate its mechanisms of action and potential clinical applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Phoenixin (PNX) is a new neuropeptide identified in 2013 as a result of bioinformatics analyses of conserved peptide sequences in human genome data (Billert et al., 2020). PNX is described as a neuropeptide derived from the C-terminal region of small integral membrane protein 20, also known as Smim20 (C4orf52) precursor (Lyu et al., 2013; Billert et al., 2020). PNX is a highly conserved neuropeptide in humans, rodents, and various vertebrate species (Yosten et al., 2013), and it has two main sequences, Phoenixin-14 (PNX-14) and Phoenixin-20 (PNX-20) (Kołodziejcki et al., 2021). Additionally, it has been reported that isoforms of PNX with 17, 26, 36, and 42 amino acids may be present (Yosten et al., 2013; Cowan et al., 2015). Although PNX-14 and PNX-20 have similar biological activity, it is known that non-amidated PNX is inactive. These findings indicate that PNX has a highly conserved structure among species (Yosten et al., 2013). This high level of conservation suggests that the peptide may play a physiologically significant role in mammals (Stein et al., 2018). Recent studies have demonstrated that biological regulatory molecules such as adipokines and neuropeptides exert multifaceted effects on metabolic, cardiovascular, inflammatory, and neuroendocrine systems (Geçmez Cahan & Bayramoğlu Akkoyun, 2025; Liang et al., 2022). In this context, it is thought that PNX also plays regulatory roles in different physiological systems (Billert et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2022). The potential roles of PNX in various physiological processes are summarized in Figure 1.

In terms of its distribution in the brain, initial studies have highlighted that PNX is found in high amounts in the hypothalamus region of rats. In subsequent

detailed examinations, this neuropeptide was found predominantly in different subregions of the hypothalamus (magnocellular and parvocellular supraoptic nucleus, dorsal hypothalamus, zona incerta, ventromedial hypothalamus, lateral hypothalamus, perifornical area, arcuate nucleus, supraoptic retrochiasmatic nucleus, and to a lesser extent, the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) regions) in cells approximately 10–15 µm in diameter. In addition to the hypothalamus, moderate levels of PNX immunoreactivity have also been detected in other brain regions such as the substantia nigra, Edinger–Westphal nucleus, nucleus tractus solitarius, dorsal motor nucleus of the vagus, and area postrema. It has also been detected in the pituitary gland and its associated areas (Yosten et al., 2013). Further studies have revealed that PNX is also found in the spinal cord (Lyu et al., 2013).

PNX is found not only in the brain but also in other parts of the body. In the initial studies conducted for this purpose, it was determined that it is also present in the heart, thymus, esophagus, and stomach. Lower levels were detected in the spleen, pancreas, lungs, and kidneys, whereas considerably lower levels were observed in the intestines (Yosten et al., 2013). Recent studies have shown that it is present in certain regions of the small intestine and in specific cell groups in the pancreas (Prinz et al., 2017). In addition, its presence has been detected in some cellular extensions in the skin (Cowan et al., 2015). In contrast, PNX has not been found in studies conducted on testicular tissue (Yosten et al., 2013; Prinz et al., 2017; Rocca et al., 2018). Therefore, the testes have generally been used as a negative control in the studies conducted (Rocca et al., 2018). In light of all this information, while the PNX-20 isoform is

predominantly found in the brain, the PN_X-14 isoform is more commonly found in the spinal cord and heart (Yosten et al., 2013; Lyu et al., 2013).

2. MECHANISM OF ACTION OF PN_X

PN_X is known as a reproductive peptide that primarily regulates the expression of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) receptors (Yosten et al., 2013). It is known to perform several functions, such as increasing luteinizing hormone (LH) release, enhancing messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) expression in GnRH and kisspeptin neurons (Treen et al., 2016), delaying the onset of estrus (Stein et al., 2016), and increasing plasma vasopressin levels (Gasparini et al., 2018). It is suggested that these effects may occur through the G protein-coupled receptor 173 (GPR173) (Schalla & Stengel, 2018).

GPR173 is identified as a putative receptor for PN_X (Billert et al., 2020) and belongs to the subfamily of G protein-coupled receptors known as super conserved receptors expressed in brain (SREB) (Matsumoto et al., 2000). The high conservation of the protein-coding mRNA region of this receptor among vertebrate species highlights its physiological significance (Larco et al., 2013a). GPR173 is widely expressed in the brain, ovaries, and small intestines (Matsumoto et al., 2000). However, it is estimated that PN_X interacts not only with GPR173 but also with other receptors (such as GPR15 and GPR25) (Treen et al., 2016).

This receptor structurally consists of 7 helical regions that span the cell membrane. Especially in the intracellular part, there are phosphorylation sites. Additionally, there are regions in its structure that can undergo ubiquitination and specific amino acids that

facilitate ligand binding. These features affect both the stability and function of the receptor (Schalla & Stengel, 2018).

It is stated that GPR173 shares structural similarities with GnRH and LH receptors. This similarity suggests that the relevant receptor, along with the PN_X and GnRH systems, may play a role together in reproductive functions, and it is particularly significant in terms of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis (Schalla & Stengel, 2018). In addition, it is suggested that the memory-enhancing and anxiolytic effects of PN_X may also occur through the GnRH system. This hypothesis is supported by the demonstration that these effects disappear with the application of the GnRH receptor antagonist Cetrorelix (Larco et al., 2013b; Schalla & Stengel, 2018). Current evidence supports that GPR173 is an important candidate receptor for PN_X; however, further studies are needed to elucidate the specificity of the ligand–receptor interaction (Billert et al., 2020).

3. THE EFFECTS OF PHOENIXIN

3.1. Reproduction

In the original study describing PN_X, PN_X was identified as a new reproductive peptide. Indeed, the first identified biological effect is its ability to increase GnRH-controlled LH release (Yosten et al., 2013). Although it has been determined that it is primarily released from the anterior pituitary gland, it has been found that it does not increase LH release on its own in studies conducted on female rats. It has been observed that PN_X-20 increases the secretion of LH stimulated by GnRH. Additionally, in the pituitary gland, PN_X increases the expression of GnRH receptors. In a study conducted on rats, which

showed that PN_X plays a role in the regulation of gonadotropin release, it was observed that the administration of PN_X-20 i.c.v. stimulated LH release (Stein et al., 2016), and in the same model, it was reported that it increased serum follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and testosterone levels without causing changes in GnRH levels. Notably, the similar brain distribution of PN_X and nesfatin-1 raises the possibility of functional interaction. The ability of both peptides to increase FSH, LH, and testosterone levels further supports this possibility (Guvenc et al., 2019). Additionally, it is stated that PN_X stimulates the secretion of GnRH and kisspeptin in hypothalamic neurons through the activation of the intracellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate/protein kinase A (cAMP/PKA) signaling pathway and the cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB) transcription factor (Treen et al., 2016).

In one of the studies conducted on female rats, it was recorded that the suppression of PN_X expression in the pituitary gland caused a delay of 2-3 days in the next estrous cycle (Yosten et al., 2013). It has been determined that the decrease in mRNA expression of the GPR173 receptor, which is thought to mediate the effects of PN_X, is associated with the prolongation of the diestrus phase in the pituitary gland (Stein et al., 2016). Therefore, PN_X is an important factor in the regulation of the ovarian cycle (Liang et al., 2022).

It has been reported that PN_X is also expressed in the ovaries (Kalamon et al., 2020) and ovarian follicles. It has been found that PN_X-14 stimulates cell proliferation in human granulosa cells and the maturation of ovarian follicles, increasing the number of ovulated oocytes. It has also been confirmed that these processes are associated with the activation of

the cAMP/PKA signaling pathway in granulosa cells, CREB phosphorylation, and increased estradiol production (Nguyen et al., 2019). In light of this evidence, it is thought that PN_X is involved in the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis. However, in conditions such as polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), it has been reported that increased PN_X production in ovarian tissue parallels the activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) and protein kinase B (Akt) signaling pathways, which are associated with cell proliferation (Kalamon et al., 2020).

Recent studies have also indicated a potential contribution of PN_X to HPG axis regulation and stress-related reproductive dysfunction (Yosten et al., 2013; Golyszny et al., 2022). Since the activation of the HPG axis has mostly been studied in female cell and animal models, it is known that the effects of PN_X on the reproductive system are more pronounced in female individuals. Although it affects gonadal hormones to a certain extent in male rats, these effects are not always mediated through the HPG axis (Liang et al., 2022).

3.2. Food intake

Due to the presence of PN_X in certain brain regions involved in appetite regulation, such as the arcuate nucleus, PVN, and ventromedial hypothalamus, several studies have demonstrated its involvement in the regulation of food intake (Schalla & Stengel, 2018). Notably, intracerebroventricular (i.c.v.) administration of PN_X-14 in rats under light conditions resulted in increased food intake, eating speed, and meal duration, whereas a decrease in food intake was observed under dark conditions. This finding suggests that the effects of PN_X on food intake

may vary depending on experimental conditions, particularly the light–dark phase (Schalla et al., 2017). In addition to its orexigenic effects, PNx has been shown to increase the number of c-Fos-positive cells, as well as c-Fos/nesfatin-1 and NUCB2/nesfatin-1 co-expressing cells, in the medial part of the nucleus of the solitary tract (NTS), the supraoptic nucleus, and the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) (Friedrich et al., 2019; Stengel et al., 2011). Considering the anorexigenic effect of nesfatin-1, it has been suggested that PNx and nesfatin-1 may exert opposing effects in the regulation of food intake (Stengel et al., 2011). Additionally, it is thought that PNx may function as an orexigenic factor not only in mammals but also in fish, as demonstrated in a study on spotted scat fish (Wang et al., 2018). In contrast, a study in zebrafish reported that PNx-20 suppressed food intake following intraperitoneal (i.p.) administration. Among the findings associated with appetite suppression were increased cocaine- and amphetamine-regulated transcript (CART) mRNA expression in the hypothalamus and inhibition of orexigenic ghrelin expression in both the intestine and hypothalamus (Rajeswari et al., 2020). This discrepancy may be related to differences in the accessibility of PNx to the central nervous system and, consequently, its effects on feeding behavior, depending on the route of administration (Schalla & Stengel, 2018).

It has been reported that there is limited evidence regarding the mechanisms of appetite regulation associated with PNx in humans, and that circulating PNx levels are low in individuals with conditions such as anorexia nervosa, increasing as body weight returns to normal. In these patients, despite elevated levels of peptides such as ghrelin and neuropeptide Y, the reduced level of PNx is also noteworthy (Pałasz

et al., 2021). This observation may be related to a decrease in adipose tissue mass, given that the peptide is produced in adipocytes (Billert et al., 2018; Pałasz et al., 2021). In light of these findings, it is thought that PNx levels may be associated with nutritional status and body weight regulation (Pałasz et al., 2021). Additionally, it has been reported that the expression of Smim20 and GPR173 can be modulated by nutritional and environmental chemical factors (McIlwraith et al., 2018). In this context, Smim20 mRNA expression has been shown to be upregulated by dietary fatty acids such as palmitate, docosahexaenoic acid, and oleate; however, this effect is not associated with cAMP, nitric oxide (NO), protein kinase C (PKC), or neuroinflammatory pathways. Conversely, bisphenol A, an environmental endocrine disruptor, has been shown to regulate Smim20 expression in a sex- and cell type-dependent manner, suppressing its expression in male hypothalamic cell lines while increasing it in female cell lines, and also leading to decreased expression *in vivo* in female Wistar rats (López-Rodríguez et al., 2019). Furthermore, GPR173 expression has been reported to be downregulated in response to palmitate and bisphenol A through p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (p38 MAPK)-mediated signaling pathways (McIlwraith et al., 2019; López-Rodríguez et al., 2019).

Besides its influence on food consumption, PNx has also been suggested to contribute to the control of thirst regulation (Schalla & Stengel, 2018). In particular, PNx-20 has been reported to enhance water intake during the light phase (Schalla et al., 2017; Haddock et al., 2020). The literature also indicates that the stimulatory effect of PNx-20 on water intake can be significantly attenuated by an angiotensin receptor blocker. Additionally, the

expression of the putative receptor candidate GPR173, which mediates the effects of PNx, varies across the estrous cycle, suggesting that it may contribute to the regulation of fluid balance under different physiological conditions (Haddock et al., 2020).

3.3. Memory and anxiety

In some animal studies, it has been stated that intracerebroventricular (i.c.v.) administration of PNx-14 facilitates object recognition and spatial localization, thereby enhancing memory formation. It is also known that, via the GnRH receptor, administration into the hippocampus strengthens memory and ameliorates certain memory impairments. Although the enhancing effect of PNx-14 on hippocampal memory protection has been shown to be abolished by pre-treatment with cetrorelix, a GnRH receptor antagonist, this suggests that the effects of the peptide on memory may be mediated either directly or through downstream GnRH receptor signaling pathways. Additionally, PNx-14 has been shown to reverse cellular memory impairments induced by amyloid- β 1–42 and scopolamine (Jiang et al., 2015a). According to the findings of one study, PNx is also thought to be a potential mediator in the identification of certain cognitive disorders. However, clinical studies have reported no significant differences in PNx-14 levels in individuals with mild Alzheimer's disease or cognitive impairment. In individuals with memory problems, plasma PNx levels have been reported to show a positive correlation with certain word recall tests, whereas in individuals without advanced cognitive impairment, they are negatively correlated with logical memory performance (Yuruyen et al., 2017).

Since it is known that PNx regulates the expression of GnRH receptors, and considering that GnRH also plays a role in the regulation of anxiety responses in the brain, it is thought that PNx may also be related to anxiety. In a maze experiment conducted on mice, it has been reported that PNx-14 exhibits an anxiolytic effect (Jiang et al., 2015b). It has been demonstrated in several studies that PNx levels show a negative correlation with anxiety (Hofmann et al., 2017), and additionally, stress reduces circulating PNx levels (Schalla et al., 2020). In studies conducted on humans, findings supporting this relationship have also been reported. It has been noted that in male patients, particularly those with weight-related disorders, increased anxiety is associated with a significant decrease in plasma PNx levels (Hofmann et al., 2017).

3.4. Lipid and glucose metabolism

It emphasizes that circulating PNx levels in the literature may be related to body mass index (BMI). It has been reported that PNx levels are positively correlated with BMI, particularly in women (Ullah et al., 2017). In the studies conducted, it has been determined that GPR173 mRNA, which is thought to mediate the effects of PNx, is expressed in rodent preadipocytes and mature white adipocytes. Moreover, it is known that the PNx peptide is also produced by mature white adipocytes (Billert et al., 2018). Some in vitro experiments have shown that PNx-14 increases proliferation in preadipocytes and triggers the differentiation of preadipocytes into mature adipocytes (Billert et al., 2020). In this process, it has been demonstrated that preadipocyte differentiation into mature adipocytes is regulated through a cAMP-dependent mechanism (Billert et al.,

Fig. 1. The potential roles of PNx in some physiological processes

2018). In this context, PNx-14 is considered to play an important role in adipogenesis (Billert et al., 2020).

A pancreas-focused scan has shown that PNx is also present in the pancreatic islets of rats. It has been particularly noted that it is densely distributed around glucagon-producing alpha cells (Prinz et al., 2017). In subsequent studies, it has been demonstrated that it is found not only around alpha cells but also in insulin-producing beta cells. Additionally, PNx-14 has been reported to stimulate the proliferation of insulin-secreting beta cells in an ERK1/2 and Akt signaling pathway-dependent manner and to increase insulin secretion in these cells. Furthermore, high glucose concentrations have been shown to induce PNx secretion, whereas PNx-14 significantly enhances glucose-dependent insulin secretion through an intracellular cAMP/Epac-dependent mechanism (Billert et al., 2019). The role of PNx in the regulation of energy homeostasis has not yet been fully elucidated; therefore, further studies are required (Billert et al., 2020).

3.5. Cardiovascular System

The detection of PNx-14 at a very high level in heart tissue raises the idea that this peptide may play a role in cardiovascular functions (Yosten et al., 2013). It has been shown that PNx-14 can affect the myocardial contraction mechanism, and particularly that it achieves this effect by increasing the phosphorylation levels of intracellular Akt, endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS), and ERK1/2 proteins (Rocca et al., 2018). Although it may cause a temporary decrease in cardiac contractility under certain conditions, PNx-14 has been confirmed to support the improvement of cardiac function during reperfusion and to limit cardiac tissue damage in experimental ischemia/reperfusion models. During this process, increased activation of signaling cascades including the reperfusion injury salvage kinase (RISK) and survival activating factor enhancement (SAFE) pathways has been reported. In addition, reductions in proapoptotic mediators such as Bcl-2-associated X protein (Bax), cysteine-aspartate protease 3 (caspase-3), cytochrome c, and p38 MAPK have been observed,

while expression of the anti-apoptotic protein B-cell lymphoma-2 (Bcl-2) has been shown to increase (Rocca et al., 2018). Additionally, it has been reported that PNX-20 may have indirect effects on fluid balance and cardiovascular tone by increasing vasopressin release through the central nervous system via GPR173 (Gasparini et al., 2018).

3.6. Inflammation

In experimental studies, it has been explained that PNX-14 and PNX-20 exhibited significant anti-inflammatory effects against inflammatory stimuli such as lipopolysaccharide and oxygen-glucose deprivation (Liang et al., 2022). These anti-inflammatory effects have been associated with decreased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), suppression of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, and enhancement of antioxidant capacity, including increased reduced glutathione (GSH) levels (Ma et al., 2020). Additionally, PNX suppresses inflammatory signaling pathways in microglia and astrocytes, reducing nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) activation and inhibiting the NOD-like receptor family pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome response. In endothelial cells, it exerts a protective effect by reducing oxidative stress and adhesion molecules, thereby maintaining vascular barrier integrity (Wei et al., 2021). These effects suggest a role in limiting tissue damage in both the brain endothelium and peripheral tissues (Liang et al., 2022).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, PNX stands out as a versatile neuropeptide thought to play a role in many

physiological processes such as reproduction, energy balance, food intake, memory, inflammation, and metabolic regulation. Its widespread distribution in the central nervous system and peripheral tissues, along with its highly conserved structure across species, suggests that it may perform physiologically significant functions. However, the current literature on the biological effects of PNX still contains many gaps. Although it is accepted that the effects of PNX are mainly mediated through GPR173, the specificity of the receptor–ligand relationship has not yet been fully clarified. Additionally, variability in administration routes, doses, experimental models, and PNX isoforms used across studies makes it difficult to directly compare findings. In particular, there is a need for more comprehensive studies on the intracellular signaling mechanisms of PNX, its interactions between different physiological systems, and its long-term effects. It is thought that future experimental and clinical studies will contribute to a more detailed understanding of PNX's mechanisms of action, bioavailability, and potential therapeutic applications. In this context, PNX is considered one of the neuropeptides that may gain increasing importance in elucidating physiological and pathophysiological processes.

In conclusion, spermatogenesis was more active in testicular tissue and an increased tendency towards spermatogonia levels was observed in the group treated with inulin. The findings suggest that inulin may have positive effects on the male reproductive system. However, quantitative analyses and further studies at the molecular level are needed to better demonstrate this effect.

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